

frequently rearranged in advanced T-cell lymphomas FRAT regulator of WNT signaling pathway 1 (FRAT1) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid ID : orcid.org/0000-0001-7027-5788

Address : 104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Corresponding author email : sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com

Abstract

FRAT1 is homologous to GSK3 binding protein (GBP), that is known to act as a positive regulator of WNT signaling by stabilizing β -catenin. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 FRAT1 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for FRAT1-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr FRAT1 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

¹Aspects of unpublished work were presented in a poster session at Cell Symposia: Technology. Biology. Data Science, 9-11 October 2016, Berkeley, California, USA.

1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of 71C_3 (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search done by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order FRAT1 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination,

then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. frequently rearranged in advanced T-cell lymphomas FRAT regulator of WNT signaling pathway 1 (FRAT1)

Embi et al. [4] purified a glycogen synthase kinase (GSK) from rabbit skeletal muscle by precipitation with ammonium sulphate, chromatography on DEAE-cellulose and chromatography on hydroxy-apatite. This enzyme was highly specific for glycogen synthase and was separated from virtually all phosphatase and casein kinase activity by the chromatography on DEAE-cellulose. Further, the activity of this enzyme was unaffected by cyclic AMP, cyclic GMP, calcium ions, calcium ions plus calmodulin, and the specific protein inhibitor of cyclic-AMP-dependent protein kinase. They observed that the properties of the enzyme demonstrated that it was distinct from both cyclic-AMP-dependent protein kinase and phosphorylase kinase, the two well characterized glycogen synthase kinases in skeletal muscle. This enzyme was therefore termed GSK3. The phosphorylation of glycogen synthase by GSK3 reached a plateau near 1.5 molecule phosphate incorporated per subunit under optimal conditions. Finally, glycogen synthase was phosphorylated by cyclic-AMP-dependent protein kinase, phosphorylase kinase and GSK3, using conditions where the phosphorylation by any one protein kinase reached a plateau near one molecule of phosphate incorporated per subunit. These results implied that each protein kinase preferentially phosphorylated a different site(s) on glycogen synthase, which was confirmed by the amino acid sequence analysis later on.

Acceleration of lymphomagenesis in oncogene-bearing transgenic mice by slow-transforming retroviruses has proven a valuable tool in identifying cooperating oncogenes. Jonkers et al. [5] modified this protocol to search for genes that could collaborate with the transgene in later stages of tumor development. Propagation of tumors induced by Moloney murine leukemia virus (M-MuLV) in E μ -PIM1 or H2-K-MYC transgenic mice by transplantation to syngeneic hosts permitted proviral tagging of 'progression' genes. They identified a novel gene, designated Frat1 (in this article mFRAT1), upon molecular cloning of common proviral insertion sites that were detected preferentially in transplanted tumors. They further cloned and sequenced both the mouse Frat1 (mFRAT1) gene and its human counterpart (hFRAT1), the encoded proteins of which were highly homologous. Upon infection with a mFRAT1-IRES-lacZ retrovirus, they observed that tumor cell lines with high expression of MYC and PIM1 acquired an additional selective advantage in vivo, which underscored the role of mFRAT1 in tumor progression, and the ability of mFRAT1 to collaborate with PIM1

and MYC in lymphomagenesis.

Dorsal accumulation of β -catenin in early *Xenopus* embryos is required for body axis formation. Evidence has indicated that β -catenin is dorsally stabilized by the localized inhibition of the kinase X-GSK3, utilizing a novel WNT ligand-independent mechanism. Using a two-hybrid screen, Yost et al. [6] identified GBP, a maternal X-GSK3-binding protein that is homologous to a T cell protooncogene in three well-conserved domains. They observed that GBP inhibits *in vivo* phosphorylation by X-GSK3, and ectopic GBP expression induced an axis by stabilizing β -catenin within *Xenopus* embryos. **Using the similarity of GBP to T cell proto-oncogene FRAT1 by Jonkers et al. [5] and a human EST, they demonstrate that GBP contains a highly conserved domain required for GSK3 binding and inhibition.** They observed that both the mouse and human proteins contained three regions that are well-conserved within GBP. A comparison of GBP and Frat1/FRAT1 showed that domain I was 63% identical, II was 70% identical, and III was 83% identical. Their studies with GBP provide a basis for understanding the proliferation of lymphoma cells, that overexpress Frat1. Because Frat1 contains the conserved domain III, it is likely to bind and inhibit GSK3, and they predicted that it stimulated T cell lymphoma proliferation by decreasing GSK3 function. In support of this, Beals et al. [7] have shown that GSK3 acts as a negative regulator of NF-ATc (nuclear factor activated in T cells).

GSK3 activity can also be inhibited in response to Wnt growth factor signaling. Cytoplasmic β -catenin is central to the transmission of Wnt signals to the nucleus; in the absence of Wnt signaling, β -catenin is phosphorylated by GSK3, which targets β -catenin for degradation via ubiquitin-dependent proteolysis. In response to Wnt signals, however, GSK3 activity toward β -catenin is inhibited, resulting in the stabilization and accumulation of β -catenin and the activation of TCF/LEF-1 transcription factors. Further, genetic studies have shown that DVL, a cytoplasmic protein downstream of Wnt receptors, is essential for transmitting WNT signals to GSK3. AXIN interacts with DVL and, in addition, binds both GSK3 and β -catenin, thus facilitating GSK3-mediated phosphorylation of β -catenin. Consequently, dissociation of the GSK3/AXIN/ β -catenin complex prevents GSK3-mediated phosphorylation of β -catenin, resulting in its stabilization. Jonkers et al. [5] have a proposed mechanism for WNT-induced dissociation of the GSK3/AXIN/ β -catenin complex which involves the mammalian protein FRAT1.

To understand the mechanism by which DVL acts through GSK to regulate LEF-1, Li et al. [8] investigated the roles of AXIN and FRAT1 in WNT-mediated activation of LEF-1 in mammalian cells. They found that DVL interacted with AXIN and with FRAT1, both of which interacted with GSK. They also found that DVL, AXIN and GSK can form a ternary complex bridged by AXIN, and that FRAT1 could be recruited into this complex probably by DVL. Their observation that the DVL-binding domain of either FRAT1 or AXIN was able to inhibit WNT1-induced LEF-1 activation suggested that the interactions between DVL and AXIN and between DVL and FRAT1 may be important for WNT signaling pathway. Furthermore, WNT1 appeared to promote the disintegration of the FRAT1-DVL-GSK-AXIN complex, resulting in the dissociation of GSK from AXIN. Thus, formation of the quaternary complex may be an important step in WNT signaling, by which DVL recruits FRAT1, leading to FRAT1-mediated dissociation of GSK from AXIN.

Now, AXIN is a negative regulator of embryonic axis formation in vertebrates, which acts through a WNT signal transduction pathway involving the serine/threonine kinase GSK3 and β -catenin. It has been shown to have distinct binding sites for GSK3 and β -catenin and to promote the phosphorylation of β -catenin and its consequent degradation thus inhibiting signaling through β -catenin. Hsu et al. [9] report the results of a yeast two-hybrid screen for proteins that interact with the C-terminal third of AXIN, a region in which no binding sites for other proteins have previously been identified. They found that AXIN can bind to the catalytic subunit of the serine/threonine protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A) through a domain between amino acids 632 and 836. Their results suggested that PP2A might interact with the AXIN-APC-GSK3- β -catenin complex, where it could modulate the effect of GSK3 on β -catenin or other proteins in the complex.

Willert et al. [10] show that AXIN is dephosphorylated in response to WNT signaling and dephosphorylated AXIN binds β -catenin less efficiently than the phosphorylated form, thus disengaging β -catenin from the degradation machinery. The AXIN-dependent phosphorylation of β -catenin catalysed by GSK3, is inhibited during embryogenesis. This protects β -catenin against ubiquitin-dependent proteolysis, leading to its accumulation in the nucleus, where it controls the expression of genes important for development. Thomas et al. [11] demonstrated that FRATtide (a peptide corresponding to residues 188-226 of FRAT1) bound to GSK3 and prevented GSK3 from interacting with AXIN. They also observed that FRATtide blocked the GSK3-catalysed phosphorylation of AXIN and β -catenin, thus pointing to a potential mechanism by which GBP could trigger axis formation. In contrast, they also found that FRATtide did not suppress GSK3 activity towards other substrates, such as glycogen synthase and eIF2B (whose phosphorylation is independent of AXIN but dependent on a 'priming' phosphorylation). This might explain how the essential cellular functions of GSK3 can continue, despite the suppression of β -catenin phosphorylation.

Hedgepeth et al. [12] defined a 25-amino-acid sequence in AXIN that is comprised of GSK3 β interaction domain (GID). In contrast to full-length AXIN, which has been shown to antagonize WNT signaling, they found that the GID inhibited GSK3 β in vivo and activated WNT signaling. They proposed that the AXIN complex might directly regulate GSK3 β enzymatic activity in vivo. Although it is known that GID and FRATtide peptides have a similar functionality, the GSK3 binding domains in FRAT and AXIN do not appear to have homologous amino acid sequences.

Bax et al. [13] described the crystal structures of isolated tyrosine 216-phosphorylated GSK3 and of a complex of GSK3 with FRATtide and a sulfate ion. Structures of uncomplexed Tyr216 phosphorylated GSK3 and of its complex with a peptide and a sulfate ion both showed the activation loop adopting a conformation similar to that in the phosphorylated and active forms of the related kinases CDK2 and ERK2. The sulfate ion, adjacent to Val214 on the activation loop, represented the binding site for the phosphoserine residue on 'primed' substrates. The peptide FRATtide formed a helix-turn-helix motif in binding to the C-terminal lobe of the kinase domain, at which FRAT and AXIN compete for binding to GSK3. FRATtide (and FRAT1) does not inhibit the activity of GSK3 toward glycogen synthase (GS). GSK3 sequentially phosphorylates four serine residues on GS, in the sequence SxxxSxxxSxxxSxxxS(p), by recognizing and phosphorylating the first serine in the sequence motif SxxxS(P) (where S(p) rep-

resents a phosphoserine). Protein inhibitors such as FRAT, which appear to regulate kinase activity by modulating protein interactions within signaling complexes, might well inhibit activity toward a selected subset of substrates and might be the target for structure-based ligand design.

I present 3rd order combinations of FRAT1 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [14]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [14].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from

the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss

the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 FRAT1-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [15]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [16] and martinez implementation in Martinez [17] and Baudin et al. [18]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested FRAT1-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving FRAT1 were obtained from a full set of ${}^7C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR											
3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSLI-FRAT1-SENP2	24	25444	38488	23401	24549	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	64	19925	35266	282	20625
AES-AXINI-FRAT1	153	39308	39740	48864	34865	CSNK1D-FGF4-FRAT1	154	4058	50213	49903	6296
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	212	18126	46011	57	25507	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	296	10717	21805	2575	15715
CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	304	26037	23203	450	10918	FRAT1-NLK-SENP2	308	14795	5137	12639	16597
FOSLI-FRAT1-WNT4	372	34237	49971	11736	48629	FRAT1-FZD1-SFRP4	507	39272	1172	47699	40072
CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	519	13366	30568	2083	18784	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	534	1131	4271	13789	39755
APC-BCL9-FRAT1	599	29224	30930	45217	55567	DVL1-FOXNI-FRAT1	613	42124	2382	9631	35079
DKK1-FRAT1-SENP2	669	29229	40235	2545	51616	FOSLI-FRAT1-TLE2	675	26389	36474	6816	48298
FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	676	35197	23478	4515	23224	CXXC4-FOSLI-FRAT1	731	20058	29538	14504	27891
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-WNT5A	734	14176	29898	41568	9680	FBXW2-FGF4-FRAT1	741	34437	49723	51069	4028
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	748	50033	38113	50412	44660	CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	758	28255	42529	10768	13750
FRAT1-PORCN-SFRP4	816	23261	18955	23358	33807	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	827	10881	39520	3401	24688
FOSLI-FRAT1-FBXW4	832	28714	21515	30364	38569	FRAT1-JUN-SENP2	876	27146	34459	14780	13983
FRAT1-FZD1-FZD7	888	26968	7671	38732	41048	FRAT1-PORCN-SENP2	915	19198	9986	14436	18176
AXINI-FOXNI-FRAT1	990	1738	4384	15268	22220	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	1005	19771	7884	9479	10249
FRAT1-FZD1-LRP5	1051	34518	43038	31699	24508	FRAT1-PORCN-RHOU	1077	31453	10861	21530	17749
CCND1-FGF4-FRAT1	1105	52382	24371	40896	23694	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	1177	38200	26202	16198	34929
FOSLI-FRAT1-TCF7L1	1246	18255	19691	45038	20105	DKK1-FRAT1-FRZB	1283	35064	37595	2698	45083
APC-FOXNI-FRAT1	1418	596	2065	13524	33264	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	1421	24998	29856	17406	1342
DKK1-FGF4-FRAT1	1462	21926	23959	17544	31567	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	1533	9050	41138	51810	43824
FBXW1-FOXNI-FRAT1	1538	7360	6561	15328	24410	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	1570	6400	25113	13146	24103
EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	1588	28152	39282	54116	41791	FOSLI-FRAT1-LRP5	1606	10313	45532	19498	50080
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	1626	39276	40450	30425	12391	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT2B	1796	26246	45830	36444	11708
CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	1810	3252	48463	383	12590	EP300-FOXNI-FRAT1	1814	1637	5045	2015	815
FGF4-FOSLI-FRAT1	1842	39537	26432	55090	52175	BCL9-FGF4-FRAT1	1875	5789	48461	56251	35603
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	1937	45988	42307	30915	9629	DKK1-FRAT1-FZD1	1941	7211	29023	2680	47286
DAAMI-FOXNI-FRAT1	1981	44098	29909	11384	47997	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT4	1985	2835	18017	16053	23730
FZD5-FGF4-FRAT1	1988	17464	37325	36960	11187	APC-BTRC-FRAT1	1993	4234	3760	19668	20988
CTNNB1-FRAT1-TLE1	2116	31975	20159	13284	55089	FRAT1-GSK3A-RHOU	2147	48585	3413	51070	8121
DAAMI-FGF4-FRAT1	2191	52861	50322	53931	30508	FRAT1-WNT1-WNT2B	2208	3244	1753	8833	56838
FRAT1-GSK3A-SFRP4	2238	47737	14694	38145	13213	DKK1-FOSLI-FRAT1	2248	20750	40597	26220	53540
FRAT1-FZD7-SFRP4	2265	6984	42886	29035	50691	CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FRAT1	2318	44804	22708	39543	10094
FRAT1-JUN-PPP2R1A	2465	21726	41887	23096	41465	CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	2496	24384	49297	7946	49881
FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	2530	6281	12625	8358	38149	FRAT1-JUN-PPP2CA	2547	32152	28002	1650	1276
CTNNB1-FRAT1-WIF1	2625	18691	37238	24416	4230	FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	2638	38412	1286	35232	13767
DVL1-FGF4-FRAT1	2664	45629	31255	34356	19416	FRAT1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	2692	5241	18995	27536	35730
CSNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	2744	18327	34701	8594	2661	CTBPI-FRAT1-WNT4	2821	37523	56525	1417	51685
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	2842	9594	30978	23790	51147	FRAT1-JUN-LRP5	2861	38548	27221	17003	13998
FRAT1-JUN-WNT3A	2877	41865	29807	34170	11250	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	2894	23698	18152	32	32646
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-RHOU	2910	38029	54971	19935	51723	CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-FZD1	2935	24095	30151	22445	24470
FRAT1-FBXW4-WNT3A	2950	1626	150	55124	17849	FRAT1-PORCN-TCF7	3001	18766	42465	28851	20276
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7	3032	30172	40041	39760	42770	CTNNB1-FRAT1-WNT4	3049	31688	29436	13852	32929
CSNK1G1-FGF4-FRAT1	3087	3833	51164	49600	29524	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	3094	24225	44587	43882	21321
CCND1-FRAT1-FZD8	3095	44826	16342	57124	29952	DAAMI-FRAT1-FZD1	3098	48916	26712	40838	53076
FOSLI-FRAT1-FZD7	3142	34552	21454	20799	55831	FRAT1-WIF1-WNT4	3157	3802	25184	32202	1523
FZD5-CTNNBIP1-FRAT1	3164	40626	31787	13769	20789	FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3217	49686	3676	49905	14302
FZD5-FOXNI-FRAT1	3239	1614	3233	20068	5777	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	3310	15749	16154	12064	34806
FRAT1-WIF1-WNT3A	3328	15377	26382	55074	7682	FGF4-FRAT1-LEF1	3378	28956	25427	26696	11917
FRAT1-JUN-TLE2	3416	30940	881	14082	28776	FGF4-FRAT1-T	3423	44186	35087	36000	23427
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	3542	41044	29584	5685	51990	CSNK1D-FRAT1-FZD1	3569	4219	52992	30046	47083
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2R1A	3641	17091	37502	41949	11356	BTRC-FOXNI-FRAT1	3675	26618	6170	28752	42168
FRAT1-FZD1-TCF7	3848	22218	19562	49291	40637	CSNK1G1-CTNNBIP1-FRAT1	3861	2169	25070	15462	45122
FRAT1-FZD1-WNT4	3864	17916	29682	40787	38438	FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B	3884	47252	4540	55696	35586
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	3929	35214	17635	44956	38660	CCND3-FGF4-FRAT1	3979	45710	31230	52987	44235
FOSLI-FRAT1-WNT5A	3989	11766	16292	43205	16137	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2B	4026	15233	43434	56478	23693
DKK1-FOXNI-FRAT1	4029	12980	50095	12148	39677	FOSLI-FRAT1-WNT3A	4035	2654	13405	47524	18665
FBXW2-FOXNI-FRAT1	4037	3650	18095	22100	31935	APC-CCND1-FRAT1	4041	16166	3819	56694	45787
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	4074	18571	5441	22722	18400	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	4096	7150	14882	4380	42041
FRAT1-JUN-SFRP1	4122	39180	11075	7077	30063	FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	4132	14097	12408	18181	22475
FRAT1-NKD1-WNT2B	4145	29853	29809	31718	30950	CSNK1G1-DVL2-FRAT1	4160	46593	24765	28311	27782
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2CA	4204	33092	39327	31761	14446	CCND3-FOXNI-FRAT1	4217	35968	4531	12204	31006
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-PPP2R1A	4272	14548	33170	16600	48598	FRAT1-PORCN-FBXW4	4346	15930	19660	14012	11065
FRAT1-GSK3A-PITX2	4363	56251	2247	18588	44926	FRAT1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	4367	13258	9450	48551	44914

Table 1: Rankings of RHOU-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSLI-FRAT1-SEN2	15910	20828	47008	39310	20122	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	4615	7359	56816	34657	49785
AES-AXIN1-FRAT1	40971	25953	19442	7499	29768	CSNK1D-FGF4-FRAT1	4624	3572	29726	25608	46279
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	38894	11877	48833	6512	54567	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	7404	4364	36104	35047	22551
CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	14668	46919	1016	36914	42585	FRAT1-NLK-SEN2	47712	35472	55874	27952	35046
FOSLI-FRAT1-WNT4	29015	37923	40684	6763	23547	FRAT1-FZD1-SFRP4	36301	34978	23479	43112	29806
CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	14983	16373	55100	8101	42887	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	32436	4345	56234	697	36071
APC-BCL9-FRAT1	26218	9041	38872	14650	34154	DVL1-FOXN1-FRAT1	5430	52202	38249	34820	8736
DKK1-FRAT1-SEN2	5714	28221	7591	6962	28179	FOSLI-FRAT1-TLE2	33776	19243	42932	10498	52900
FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	21621	33205	53792	38197	10593	CXXC4-FOSLI-FRAT1	46607	15174	26086	25252	40912
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-WNT5A	14700	16677	7050	19562	51259	FBXW2-FGF4-FRAT1	2026	20472	4852	3031	14653
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	28349	55075	50998	56838	16856	CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	23718	42906	43026	55168	47523
FRAT1-PORCN-SFRP4	3261	12036	26076	48387	48335	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	6745	11128	54253	54080	39603
FOSLI-FRAT1-FBXW4	36692	36234	15133	298	43524	FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	8350	32873	42151	5535	36295
FRAT1-FZD1-FZD7	44345	11549	24568	50638	31308	FRAT1-PORCN-SEN2	1688	40659	28876	5431	52097
AXIN1-FOXN1-FRAT1	11810	7964	53217	15423	27549	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	51049	30143	52377	44271	42168
FRAT1-FZD1-LRP5	50543	21546	48624	49795	45309	FRAT1-PORCN-RHOU	3460	15685	47256	50127	56007
CCND1-FGF4-FRAT1	17956	51509	45262	19015	2384	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	35091	47221	26189	44148	8318
FOSLI-FRAT1-TCF7L1	6305	18815	46524	19747	38837	DKK1-FRAT1-FRZB	6565	25423	24574	19597	32464
APC-FOXN1-FRAT1	3161	1596	53917	10232	43563	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	5682	22392	33504	50525	42228
DKK1-FGF4-FRAT1	4148	10125	11678	13090	51021	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	2503	5561	19946	26820	16773
FBXW11-FOXN1-FRAT1	1470	1272	34561	8385	2950	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	50800	21515	31927	26376	27004
EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	2201	12179	25784	4990	46565	FOSLI-FRAT1-LRP5	50831	2200	13168	50933	31960
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	25869	45197	28755	12226	10788	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT2B	5506	22998	20346	48317	52835
CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	23317	429	29024	48013	32482	EP300-FOXN1-FRAT1	1892	1651	56769	4475	20697
FGF4-FOSLI-FRAT1	36045	19108	7369	17738	6729	BCL9-FGF4-FRAT1	10271	2379	18017	2603	50852
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	5995	44498	42143	51675	21496	DKK1-FRAT1-FZD1	19164	9285	16756	11451	2938
DAAMI-FOXN1-FRAT1	1220	38890	41515	23629	2845	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT4	6345	412	40450	45568	49626
FZD5-FGF4-FRAT1	2785	12058	29953	16069	54728	APC-BTRC-FRAT1	3582	6272	14221	27977	50407
CTNNB1-FRAT1-TLE1	41519	28306	20939	29010	23814	FRAT1-GSK3A-RHOU	657	46931	57041	43942	44978
DAAMI-FGF4-FRAT1	2382	47605	3660	19613	8387	FRAT1-WNT1-WNT2B	2332	26098	25477	468	37575
FRAT1-GSK3A-SFRP4	1373	56164	57119	36102	24893	DKK1-FOSLI-FRAT1	33541	20184	16489	26495	35744
FRAT1-FZD7-SFRP4	20912	2158	13215	46716	47913	CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FRAT1	40906	34560	18359	47062	27181
FRAT1-JUN-PPP2R1A	14775	16627	12246	41797	26468	CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	10676	6045	28407	52045	39223
FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	26675	24348	52446	8545	15016	FRAT1-JUN-PPP2CA	5774	39371	22955	20982	28298
CTNNB1-FRAT1-WIF1	47615	22068	25131	13309	23212	FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	761	45444	39194	15449	37603
DVL1-FGF4-FRAT1	9073	44789	3550	38608	29637	FRAT1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	36730	6551	53507	13171	7537
CSNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	14134	8276	23947	22453	12908	CTBP1-FRAT1-WNT4	18976	14759	42598	7813	23120
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	4283	5655	31886	10011	47555	FRAT1-JUN-LRP5	30940	35744	44125	50143	9478
FRAT1-JUN-WNT3A	15147	49714	47627	40535	9810	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	31513	32492	56401	22069	45177
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-RHOU	31950	44062	33709	39051	21440	CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-FZD1	31601	25917	36204	31038	19909
FRAT1-FBXW4-WNT3A	9047	7060	50667	48783	9181	FRAT1-PORCN-TCF7	4786	11400	15229	26447	47622
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7	20412	24343	20065	18890	4704	CTNNB1-FRAT1-WNT4	47053	8184	24931	20302	11182
CSNK1G1-FGF4-FRAT1	3622	6775	28403	42516	41038	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	33906	17235	3856	45519	18398
CCND1-FRAT1-FZD8	12451	39543	30979	49430	5849	DAAMI-FRAT1-FZD1	51132	47886	29535	24747	5189
FOSLI-FRAT1-FZD7	12373	35981	36534	49365	46202	FRAT1-WIF1-WNT4	11715	10008	40620	23391	16427
FZD5-CTNNB1P1-FRAT1	9647	39623	35890	28092	27363	FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	1014	49731	56438	48125	38195
FZD5-FOXN1-FRAT1	2100	4271	49015	14785	48856	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	34751	15623	55443	44289	5640
FRAT1-WIF1-WNT3A	9771	4923	24250	54851	24596	FGF4-FRAT1-LEF1	31066	20435	17093	51607	24437
FRAT1-JUN-TLE2	16100	41040	43169	2851	12149	FGF4-FRAT1-T	32855	45074	17896	53163	5390
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	9306	45373	50696	51816	46911	CSNK1D-FRAT1-FZD1	30515	10291	41362	5174	7792
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2R1A	14510	12147	3493	8420	55974	BTRC-FOXN1-FRAT1	4169	16478	20795	41841	6870
FRAT1-FZD1-TCF7	37161	14430	23168	4044	3673	CSNK1G1-CTNNB1P1-FRAT1	33926	1534	33111	36556	16893
FRAT1-FZD1-WNT4	16352	4916	36924	16247	12510	FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B	879	52429	41443	52100	38481
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	26521	15175	17461	50164	8676	CCND3-FGF4-FRAT1	923	41417	2673	50928	9653
FOSLI-FRAT1-WNT5A	15326	11446	5784	40657	50388	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2B	4610	24427	6784	49388	29620
DKK1-FOXN1-FRAT1	3005	19928	37678	14251	30164	FOSLI-FRAT1-WNT3A	41058	173	49766	43236	36519
FBXW2-FOXN1-FRAT1	653	2418	47266	9683	6624	APC-CCND1-FRAT1	6221	23081	30204	12778	48186
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	52049	4579	56808	43475	33170	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	47257	5675	39028	27369	25057
FRAT1-JUN-SFRP1	28999	41597	51643	10105	50596	FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	6165	13829	40997	17174	24514
FRAT1-NKD1-WNT2B	51624	45676	36060	50442	21912	CSNK1G1-DVL2-FRAT1	9579	48127	29769	49213	40546
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2CA	2795	32747	21472	22562	46364	CCND3-FOXN1-FRAT1	1558	27589	45891	36973	12790
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-PPP2R1A	19452	31715	19287	3657	50902	FRAT1-PORCN-FBXW4	7781	31159	19619	12417	44285
FRAT1-GSK3A-PITX2	4495	57021	56892	56898	45139	FRAT1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	2600	1832	57133	17595	45874

Table 2: Rankings of RHOU-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of AXIN / DVL / GSK3 / WNT family -FRAT1-X combinations

In the literature review in section 2.3, we find connection of AXIN, DVL, GSK3 and WNT family members with FRAT1. Looking at the tables above, one finds the fol-

RANKING @ t_1 USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSL1-FRAT1-SENP2	11214	7586	5074	7384	41915	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	13855	16693	7772	24610	15521
AES-AXIN1-FRAT1	46658	53560	33703	37373	4417	CSNK1D-FGF4-FRAT1	43307	19656	33814	44501	13085
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	8172	787	10839	18520	17014	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	9682	502	6322	25277	1837
CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	25898	41741	14499	23277	897	FRAT1-NLK-SENP2	30840	31831	43075	52500	657
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4	11661	37114	3277	931	53168	FRAT1-FZD1-SFRP4	6038	46064	10551	4222	51537
CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	18548	15555	6549	27894	2409	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	35248	26254	44997	50913	4522
APC-BCL9-FRAT1	22056	15736	20010	27003	43325	DVL1-FOXN1-FRAT1	8406	42213	25214	3249	49498
DKK1-FRAT1-SENP2	45931	9787	52534	55862	16571	FOSL1-FRAT1-TLE2	50038	6818	42415	47626	4928
FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	8549	16613	14863	6104	42450	CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	13778	2749	16108	6403	43145
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-WNT5A	11059	21534	9005	4048	52412	FBXW2-FGF4-FRAT1	29365	49192	51013	53613	3278
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	19630	54721	9834	10848	22067	CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	2163	4891	11842	2940	40557
FRAT1-PORCN-SFRP4	22000	49118	15018	7354	55844	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	19654	576	4332	16136	19365
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	37417	42346	33119	29950	927	FRAT1-JUN-SENP2	10491	7985	11945	814	56174
FRAT1-FZD1-FZD7	4928	29461	25041	21288	39572	FRAT1-PORCN-SENP2	8802	23948	15600	4011	48205
AXIN1-FOXN1-FRAT1	2352	55910	24610	26180	53343	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	21933	31321	12151	6237	52766
FRAT1-FZD1-LRP5	45999	7487	55298	45722	9463	FRAT1-PORCN-RHOU	39358	56828	38942	45808	6638
CCND1-FGF4-FRAT1	49408	608	49216	32258	5045	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	21027	9576	20703	24611	44741
FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1	50590	19180	53417	52474	6976	DKK1-FRAT1-FRZB	7004	48427	12807	3275	48568
APC-FOXN1-FRAT1	27393	16291	3934	10975	21998	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	7869	2751	20454	26029	9961
DKK1-FGF4-FRAT1	47160	15188	35665	45961	16048	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	2172	8556	22888	20956	35669
FBXW1-FOXN1-FRAT1	21263	930	20115	10646	37562	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	27208	27395	8069	9031	35043
EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	28283	15095	9139	11230	48178	FOSL1-FRAT1-LRP5	31351	10581	42739	34529	664
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	43935	48115	50408	53433	8865	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT2B	37208	46905	41078	48022	2109
CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	14447	55550	4187	25428	10791	EP300-FOXN1-FRAT1	33439	56590	46308	36232	22363
FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1	10083	6588	8685	24287	30035	BCL9-FGF4-FRAT1	13675	4238	2100	11872	27438
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	40594	22021	35719	33231	5409	DKK1-FRAT1-FZD1	7759	49941	13874	14984	42925
DAAMI-FOXN1-FRAT1	18759	51468	15889	3356	46996	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT4	26095	16695	23293	12549	25899
FZD5-FGF4-FRAT1	55072	48238	55804	50630	3393	APC-BTRC-FRAT1	22788	28000	7246	25437	29647
CTNNB1-FRAT1-TLE1	21842	13087	15698	6945	46691	FRAT1-GSK3A-RHOU	15041	1576	21617	10248	31518
DAAMI-FGF4-FRAT1	43098	14576	37598	31986	7007	FRAT1-WNT1-WNT2B	43636	48026	38928	45488	13195
FRAT1-GSK3A-SFRP4	46587	7051	33905	51923	1338	DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1	3553	54257	16310	25765	12367
FRAT1-FZD7-SFRP4	14882	44489	27738	15369	54571	CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FRAT1	25796	21067	5577	2152	38428
FRAT1-JUN-PPP2R1A	42706	1201	38950	37080	1437	CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	27618	3778	3433	676	48257
FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	25915	28518	16997	20251	33293	FRAT1-JUN-PPP2CA	14423	55965	18214	20111	55748
CTNNB1-FRAT1-WIF1	20069	13878	9022	3674	41411	FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	35360	46417	34830	42562	36551
DVL1-FGF4-FRAT1	53484	2443	39620	49188	21470	FRAT1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	15043	943	15978	9861	49165
CSNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	34042	35885	29812	41264	26139	CTBP1-FRAT1-WNT4	45752	29806	46733	42589	25329
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	50820	53673	45701	44615	8451	FRAT1-JUN-LRP5	29615	43084	51255	56304	20967
FRAT1-JUN-WNT3A	39561	4114	49795	55106	4394	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	41126	2126	46459	30168	34144
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-RHOU	6678	8213	12006	7333	13473	CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-FZD1	4735	3219	9113	4943	21105
FRAT1-FBXW4-WNT3A	42074	26045	31970	33331	9797	FRAT1-PORCN-TCF7	8454	6029	15629	11752	23166
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7	13206	9047	6739	3717	48303	CTNNB1-FRAT1-WNT4	12261	38039	22103	26433	50328
CSNK1G1-FGF4-FRAT1	23308	12898	577	6288	40499	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	17301	5414	8956	6791	9863
CCND1-FRAT1-FZD8	1638	41273	18397	16281	42808	DAAMI-FRAT1-FZD1	75	21278	24170	10528	20861
FOSL1-FRAT1-FZD7	4534	8444	3333	12890	53657	FRAT1-WIF1-WNT4	23572	3207	18683	9445	56168
FZD5-CTNNB1P1-FRAT1	4215	48884	10975	17059	55453	FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	7872	42308	28346	8689	37391
FZD5-FOXN1-FRAT1	6227	22431	19656	19126	37370	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	1757	23783	11410	15776	43723
FRAT1-WIF1-WNT3A	38203	56268	35949	38506	8834	FGF4-FRAT1-LEF1	46318	42901	43817	54293	4339
FRAT1-JUN-TLE2	44550	5101	39931	43866	6066	FGF4-FRAT1-T	6031	46352	6222	14615	52967
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	17526	25193	23946	23550	12450	CSNK1D-FRAT1-FZD1	20960	29768	28275	10710	43347
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2R1A	40959	10690	33431	37055	7595	BTRC-FOXN1-FRAT1	7013	46922	9257	20604	31255
FRAT1-FZD1-TCF7	10451	41458	6309	13435	27945	CSNK1G1-CTNNB1P1-FRAT1	30913	54548	34626	46216	8117
FRAT1-FZD1-WNT4	19938	27077	551	7253	29402	FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B	6301	21329	27139	5381	39536
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	4589	40067	18292	17467	37330	CCND3-FGF4-FRAT1	48715	53923	52048	43197	1346
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT5A	45515	20368	53903	56229	4134	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2B	10347	1884	4787	18860	5517
DKK1-FOXN1-FRAT1	992	2798	19868	18643	17885	FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT3A	46128	6025	54609	53346	1957
FBXW2-FOXN1-FRAT1	25966	43521	3824	7597	30277	APC-CCND1-FRAT1	34552	48034	50562	35581	9031
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	26333	25024	14059	4672	56498	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	28123	53372	22683	12683	35312
FRAT1-JUN-SFRP1	46672	49178	45225	56342	997	FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	37686	56136	39369	37595	23150
FRAT1-NKD1-WNT2B	24369	20985	18036	6577	44433	CSNK1G1-DVL2-FRAT1	26556	18608	15393	7467	55267
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2CA	16216	46645	23644	20053	49567	CCND3-FOXN1-FRAT1	4221	4865	11303	8786	56136
CTNNB1P1-FRAT1-PPP2R1A	2661	17596	13691	9074	52194	FRAT1-PORCN-FBXW4	35207	8000	42127	49805	1314
FRAT1-GSK3A-PITX2	44421	52054	29767	47337	1646	FRAT1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	37276	51145	33319	42440	14079

Table 3: Rankings of RHOU-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

lowing combinations for members of AXIN along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AES-AXIN1-FRAT1 and AXIN1-FOXN1-FRAT1; for members of DVL along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DVL1-FGF4-FRAT1, DVL1-FOXN1-FRAT1, DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1 and CSNK1G1-DVL2-FRAT1; for members of GSK3 along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FRAT1-GSK3A-

RANKING @ t_1 USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2P	39777	6057	7944	11007	26753	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	4524	34402	46794	6498	8094
AES-AXINI-FRAT1	54041	39859	23750	26757	13522	CSNK1D-FGF4-FRAT1	56865	12006	918	21628	54532
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	11724	43395	50755	17676	10023	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	22778	53793	47414	21406	16409
CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	987	15768	29512	11340	7983	FRAT1-NLK-SEN2P	23247	35162	2221	25952	18481
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4	40993	13521	5723	19915	17592	FRAT1-FZD1-SFRP4	53293	7090	8075	43547	31983
CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	10737	32616	38921	7498	6441	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	25990	49738	661	19315	9889
APC-BCL9-FRAT1	33252	1706	39863	55287	50695	DVL1-FOXN1-FRAT1	8925	23233	8529	30875	33079
DKK1-FRAT1-SEN2P	14696	24294	9121	27635	46653	FOSL1-FRAT1-TLE2	15082	2010	33027	18895	57055
FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	17000	17285	9957	1367	55436	CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	9338	19582	40214	46514	45765
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-WNT5A	9313	54626	33929	10670	26211	FBXW2-FGF4-FRAT1	32866	12490	25033	47386	52804
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	12383	53362	24248	28478	2424	CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-KREMEN1	28588	7834	42573	50625	38323
FRAT1-PORCN-SFRP4	43619	53535	46222	28713	24581	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	4301	44390	15228	41861	45793
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	8229	28251	25524	20028	51893	FRAT1-JUN-SEN2P	25462	55027	16547	2227	53156
FRAT1-FZD1-FZD7	53337	3858	46272	18430	5419	FRAT1-PORCN-SEN2P	18609	31024	10863	13050	55318
AXINI-FOXN1-FRAT1	7322	33331	52762	5053	1371	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	39223	41587	3411	8849	50359
FRAT1-FZD1-LRP5	12496	5162	43552	37079	54201	FRAT1-PORCN-RHOU	50790	54552	928	2722	13751
CCND1-FGF4-FRAT1	55775	53244	46981	28495	24998	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	5493	26134	6285	2741	55395
FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1	15407	495	42575	35576	56798	DKK1-FRAT1-FRZB	41413	6602	5430	16847	48349
APC-FOXN1-FRAT1	19229	3828	17383	14340	36160	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	36507	46562	51863	10238	16814
DKK1-FGF4-FRAT1	7001	26191	47849	27541	20597	DIXDC1-FGF4-FRAT1	11311	3948	23704	36266	46313
FBXW11-FOXN1-FRAT1	1254	8187	49001	52657	39237	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	18761	55322	24209	45107	1970
EP300-FGF4-FRAT1	36332	37765	20615	3058	7021	FOSL1-FRAT1-LRP5	6391	34980	35339	17352	9847
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	52500	31836	3000	12107	9211	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT2B	20944	46462	334	27557	17691
CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	26342	36309	49368	17193	12600	EP300-FOXN1-FRAT1	43464	28924	224	55362	45013
FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1	53680	15862	18440	42387	14908	BCL9-FGF4-FRAT1	7469	4558	49181	16283	44562
FRAT1-JUN-KREMEN1	48706	41487	1000	47	11103	DKK1-FRAT1-FZD1	38427	8008	3942	26453	52306
DAAMI-FOXN1-FRAT1	2236	6345	29491	49993	51397	FRAT1-PORCN-WNT4	1204	15349	9265	36000	46519
FZD5-FGF4-FRAT1	42087	21560	32872	30207	30742	APC-BTRC-FRAT1	23852	12515	51125	11345	29980
CTNNB1-FRAT1-TLE1	43368	18642	35654	39935	7235	FRAT1-GSK3A-RHOU	4899	42629	53310	24498	13503
DAAMI-FGF4-FRAT1	56035	34324	30046	10463	21339	FRAT1-WNT1-WNT2B	56016	2730	27669	6169	12853
FRAT1-GSK3A-SFRP4	54807	41565	1356	30570	18546	DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1	35900	23175	16488	8823	46105
FRAT1-FZD7-SFRP4	8828	4956	5234	20471	40370	CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FRAT1	5810	51794	8029	23468	9661
FRAT1-JUN-PPP2R1A	50324	54822	2963	10268	16810	CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	2838	20322	35155	3949	37439
FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	6165	41726	15518	10280	22478	FRAT1-JUN-PPP2CA	18796	55637	7251	29192	8902
CTNNB1-FRAT1-WIF1	53443	45241	16624	35157	4135	FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	39172	41845	6227	25898	13956
DVL1-FGF4-FRAT1	9551	5894	23672	38313	57140	FRAT1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	9471	50181	19756	15455	51175
CSNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	18469	1863	38915	19191	36580	CTBP1-FRAT1-WNT4	42916	92	41662	39172	18130
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	51420	54605	51634	34135	52133	FRAT1-JUN-LRP5	11679	50613	3355	31012	9877
FRAT1-JUN-WNT3A	39546	53173	35042	32325	16889	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	44878	33087	4409	31710	48775
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-RHOU	26033	6207	11613	21857	49407	CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-FZD1	47307	5288	38449	53585	54627
FRAT1-FBXW4-WNT3A	43009	48789	21342	24484	14792	FRAT1-PORCN-TCF7	46228	29543	10484	18798	42652
FRAT1-JUN-TCF7	29273	24307	13115	14537	52349	CTNNB1-FRAT1-WNT4	6977	9245	34902	26822	31103
CSNK1G1-FGF4-FRAT1	17863	11935	14252	19547	33993	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	444	16817	15763	18220	54420
CCND1-FRAT1-FZD8	15394	26211	55725	50931	39842	DAAMI-FRAT1-FZD1	17036	15884	51378	28639	23124
FOSL1-FRAT1-FZD7	48659	16465	5851	11736	27945	FRAT1-WIF1-WNT4	30251	45228	4311	5672	47777
FZD5-CTNNBIP1-FRAT1	14506	10088	53335	51269	14786	FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	13207	50057	16985	12076	1552
FZD5-FOXN1-FRAT1	21521	3848	51827	51273	42626	DIXDC1-DVL2-FRAT1	20065	1974	41063	55571	41726
FRAT1-WIF1-WNT3A	41904	51607	5191	8446	11262	FGF4-FRAT1-LEF1	8132	56225	39554	8641	33570
FRAT1-JUN-TLE2	51362	47946	22696	3869	11851	FGF4-FRAT1-T	54235	14422	5818	14465	20828
CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	27974	46025	36509	52732	2302	CSNK1D-FRAT1-FZD1	35866	8723	28263	47919	5986
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2R1A	54020	46007	6706	6670	15729	BTRC-FOXN1-FRAT1	9062	46060	27336	34652	4476
FRAT1-FZD1-TCF7	51070	4996	8996	34338	20078	CSNK1G1-CTNNBIP1-FRAT1	29740	33174	48433	26773	13996
FRAT1-FZD1-WNT4	54302	4033	6680	15307	1679	FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B	24472	18839	31433	45485	12660
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	10379	19677	54361	54552	23021	CCND3-FGF4-FRAT1	39089	39612	47634	45838	53648
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT5A	10752	36063	44264	35867	55092	CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2B	28053	26349	26983	15697	12983
DKK1-FOXN1-FRAT1	42344	36861	5536	16605	46148	FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT3A	11698	1119	38201	37206	48568
FBXW2-FOXN1-FRAT1	19051	10725	55682	18968	41274	APC-CCND1-FRAT1	45548	21694	50740	24442	20616
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	4145	49061	13623	12994	32771	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	81	37116	49362	15818	45457
FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	49960	44655	2216	19219	8122	FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	54346	46674	9496	2030	10423
FRAT1-NKD1-WNT2B	5231	50362	21459	23272	47205	CSNK1G1-DVL2-FRAT1	1067	55676	22139	39406	23035
FRAT1-PORCN-PPP2CA	40340	33092	34294	8634	52771	CCND3-FOXN1-FRAT1	45838	44062	9610	45118	45684
CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-PPP2R1A	22487	8177	46965	50040	53950	FRAT1-PORCN-FBXW4	41181	53478	26508	40023	20163
FRAT1-GSK3A-PITX2	54984	44532	31462	10423	18225	FRAT1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	26270	35842	1283	29834	8226

Table 4: Rankings of RHOU-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

SFRP4, FRAT1-GSK3A-PITX2, FRAT1-GSK3A-RHOU, FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2CA, FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1, FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B and FRAT1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1; for members of WNT along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4, FRAT1-JUN-WNT2, CTNNBIP1-FRAT1-WNT5A, FRAT1-JUN-WNT3A, FRAT1-FBXW4-WNT3A, FRAT1-WIF1-WNT3A, FRAT1-FZD1-WNT4, FOSL1-FRAT1-

WNT5A, FRAT1-NKD1-WNT2B, FRAT1-NLK-WNT4, FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A, CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A, FRAT1-PORCN-WNT2B, FRAT1-PORCN-WNT4, FRAT1-WNT1-WNT2B, CTBP1-FRAT1-WNT4, CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2, CTNNB1-FRAT1-WNT4, FRAT1-WIF1-WNT4, FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B, CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2B, FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT3A and FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of CSNK family -FRAT1-X combinations

Hino et al. [19] demonstrated that DVL1, casein kinase I epsilon (CKI-epsilon/CSNK1E), and FRAI1 activated the WNT signaling pathway cooperatively. They observed that the amino acid region 228-250 of DVL1 was necessary for its binding to FRAT1, and the interaction of DVL1 with FRAT1 was enhanced by CSNK1E. Coexpression of DVL1 and FRAT1 led to accumulation of β -catenin synergistically in L cells. Depletion of CSNK1E in HeLa S3 cells led to the inhibition of WNT3A-induced phosphorylation of DVL and the binding of DVL1 to FRAT1. Furthermore, depletion of CSNK1E reduced the WNT3A-induced accumulation of β -catenin, although it did not affect the basal level of β -catenin. Their results indicated that CSNK1E-dependent phosphorylation of DVL enhanced the formation of a complex of DVL1 with FRAT1 and that this complex led to the activation of the Wnt signaling pathway. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CSNK family along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CSNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1, CSNK1G1-FGF4-FRAT1, CSNK1D-FGF4-FRAT1, CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FRAT1, CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1, CSNK1D-FRAT1-FZD1, CSNK1G1-CTNNBIP1-FRAT1 and CSNK1G1-DVL2-FRAT1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of LRP5-FRAT1-X combinations

Low density lipoprotein receptor-related protein 5 (LRP5) is a WNT co-receptor involved in the activation of the β -catenin signaling pathway. Using the yeast two-hybrid system, Hay et al. [20] identified FRAT1 as a protein interacting with the cytoplasmic domain of LRP5 and demonstrated that LRP5/FRAT1 interaction is involved in β -catenin nuclear translocation and TCF1 transcriptional activation. The addition of WNT3A or overexpression of constitutively active truncated LRP5 (LRP5C) induced FRAT1 recruitment to the cell membrane, while overexpression of a dominant negative form of DVL showed that this protein positively affected LRP5/FRAT1 interaction. Further, AXIN interacts with LRP5 and which is recruited to the membrane through this interaction, was found to co-immunoprecipitate with FRAT1 and LRP5. Based on these observations, they proposed that recruitment of AXIN and FRAT1 to the membrane by LRP5 led to both AXIN degradation and FRAT1-mediated inhibition of GAK3. As a consequence, β -catenin was no longer bound to AXIN or phosphorylated by GSK3, thus resulting in TCF1 activation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of LRP5 family along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FRAT1-FZD1-LRP5, CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5, FOSL1-

FRAT1-LRP5 and FRAT1-JUN-LRP5. As β -catenin was no longer bound to AXIN or phosphorylated by GSK3, thus resulting in TCF1 activation, due to the upstream AXIN-FRAT1-GSK3 interaction, looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of TCF family along with FRAT1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1, FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1, FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1, FRAT1-JUN-TCF7, FRAT1-FZD1-TCF7 and FRAT1-PORCN-TCF7. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of GSK3-FRAT1-X combinations - special case

Using a two-hybrid screen, Yost et al. [6] identified GBP, a maternal X-GSK3-binding protein that is homologous to a T cell protooncogene in three well-conserved domains. They observed that GBP inhibits *in vivo* phosphorylation by X-GSK3, and ectopic GBP expression induced an axis by stabilizing β -catenin within *Xenopus* embryos. Using the similarity of GBP to T cell proto-oncogene FRAT1 by Jonkers et al. [5] and a human EST, they demonstrate that GBP contains a highly conserved domain required for GSK3 binding and inhibition. Not recorded in the above tables, but the data available from supplementary files, one finds the following combinations for members of GSK3 family along with FRAT1 (from among top 5000 rankings), to be prominent at 3rd order level - FRAT1-GSK3B-KREMEN1, FRAT1-GSK3B-SEN2, FRAT1-GSK3A-TLE2, FRAT1-GSK3A-TCF7, FRAT1-GSK3A-WIF1, FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2R1A, FRAT1-GSK3A-RHO, FRAT1-GSK3A-NLK, FRAT1-GSK3A-PPP2CA, FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2B, FRAT1-GSK3A-GSK3B, FRAT1-GSK3A-KREMEN1, FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT4, FRAT1-GSK3A-SFRP4, FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT2, FRAT1-GSK3B-TCF7, FRAT1-GSK3B-TCF7L1, FRAT1-GSK3A-SFRP1, FRAT1-GSK3A-FBXW4, FRAT1-GSK3A-JUN, FRAT1-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1, FRAT1-GSK3A-WNT3A, FRAT1-GSK3B-T, FRAT1-GSK3A-PITX2, DKK1-FRAT1-GSK3B, FRAT1-GSK3A-PORCN, FRAT1-GSK3B-WNT2B and FRAT1-GSK3A-LRP5.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of FRAT1 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the FRAT1, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

Acknowledgments

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and late Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For FRAT1, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

References

- [1] T. S. Gujral, G. MacBeath, A system-wide investigation of the dynamics of wnt signaling reveals novel phases of transcriptional regulation, *PLoS one* 5 (2010) e10024.
- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [4] N. Embi, D. B. Rylatt, P. Cohen, Glycogen synthase kinase-3 from rabbit skeletal muscle: Separation from cyclic-amp-dependent protein kinase and phosphorylase kinase, *European Journal of biochemistry* 107 (1980) 519–527.
- [5] J. Jonkers, H. C. Korswagen, D. Acton, M. Breuer, A. Berns, Activation of a novel proto-oncogene, *frat1*, contributes to progression of mouse t-cell lymphomas, *The EMBO journal* (1997).
- [6] C. Yost, G. H. Farr, S. B. Pierce, D. M. Ferkey, M. M. Chen, D. Kimelman, Gbp, an inhibitor of gsk-3, is implicated in xenopus development and oncogenesis, *Cell* 93 (1998) 1031–1041.
- [7] C. R. Beals, C. M. Sheridan, C. W. Turck, P. Gardner, G. R. Crabtree, Nuclear export of nf-atc enhanced by glycogen synthase kinase-3, *Science* 275 (1997) 1930–1933.
- [8] L. Li, H. Yuan, C. D. Weaver, J. Mao, G. H. FarrIII, D. J. Sussman, J. Jonkers, D. Kimelman, D. Wu, Axin and *frat1* interact with *dvl* and *gsk*, bridging *dvl* to *gsk* in wnt-mediated regulation of *lef-1*, *The EMBO journal* (1999).

- [9] W. Hsu, L. Zeng, F. Costantini, Identification of a domain of axin that binds to the serine/threonine protein phosphatase 2a and a self-binding domain, *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 274 (1999) 3439–3445.
- [10] K. Willert, S. Shibamoto, R. Nusse, Wnt-induced dephosphorylation of axin releases β -catenin from the axin complex, *Genes & development* 13 (1999) 1768–1773.
- [11] G. M. Thomas, S. Frame, M. Goedert, I. Nathke, P. Polakis, P. Cohen, A gsk3-binding peptide from *frat1* selectively inhibits the gsk3-catalysed phosphorylation of axin and β -catenin, *FEBS letters* 458 (1999) 247–251.
- [12] C. M. Hedgepeth, M. A. Deardorff, K. Rankin, P. S. Klein, Regulation of glycogen synthase kinase 3 β and downstream wnt signaling by axin, *Molecular and cellular biology* 19 (1999) 7147–7157.
- [13] B. Bax, P. S. Carter, C. Lewis, A. R. Guy, A. Bridges, R. Tanner, G. Pettman, C. Mannix, A. A. Culbert, M. J. Brown, et al., The structure of phosphorylated gsk-3 β complexed with a peptide, *frattide*, that inhibits β -catenin phosphorylation, *Structure* 9 (2001) 1143–1152.
- [14] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [15] S. Da Veiga, Global sensitivity analysis with dependence measures, *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation* 85 (2015) 1283–1305.
- [16] A. Saltelli, Making best use of model evaluations to compute sensitivity indices, *Computer physics communications* 145 (2002) 280–297.
- [17] J. Martinez, Analyse de sensibilité globale par décomposition de la variance, *Presentation in Journée des GdR Ondes & Mascot* 13 (2011) 207.
- [18] M. Baudin, K. Boumhaout, T. Delage, B. Iooss, J.-M. Martinez, Numerical stability of sobol’indices estimation formula, in: *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Sensitivity Analysis of Model Output (SAMO 2016)*, volume 30, 2016, pp. 50–51.
- [19] S.-i. Hino, T. Michiue, M. Asashima, A. Kikuchi, Casein kinase ϵ enhances the binding of *dvl-1* to *frat-1* and is essential for wnt-3a-induced accumulation of β -catenin, *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 278 (2003) 14066–14073.
- [20] E. Hay, C. Faucheu, I. Suc-Royer, R. Touitou, V. Stiot, B. Vayssière, R. Baron, S. Roman-Roman, G. Rawadi, Interaction between *lrp5* and *frat1* mediates the activation of the wnt canonical pathway, *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 280 (2005) 13616–13623.